

Production Estimation Technique Using Material Balance Equation in Hydraulically Fractured Unconventional Shale Gas Reservoirs

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ABSTRACT

The fluid flow in a multi-scale porous medium raises the forecasting output's complexity using a statistical model in an unconventional shale gas reservoir. On the other hand, the material balance approach simplifies defining the dynamics of the seepage equation's solving mechanism and offers a fitting tool for theoretical study and field implementation. The generated partition of the material balance equation involves the matrix, natural and artificial fractures, integrating the pressure drop and partition propagation law, and then placed forward a creative and design method for evaluating dynamic partitioning based on the seepage characteristics in the fracture network of a horizontal-well. Through the model and implementation example, the associated measurement parameters and suitable mechanism of air content, water and gas production rate, and constraints such as fracturing parameters, physical properties, adsorption, imbibition, and production efficiency are formulated based on the material balance theory and the characteristics of the shale gas reservoir. The effectively forecast production trend, in particular, revealed the shift rules of gas supply ratio in different production periods, providing the foundation for an in-depth understanding of seepage characteristics.

Keywords: Shale gas; material balance equation; production prediction; Fracture; Desorption; Infiltration absorption

INTRODUCTION

The material balance equation is a conventional and advanced reservoir engineering approach for measuring reserve. Today, the gas reservoir material balance equation has been extended to incorporate functions such as material balance equation partitioning, productivity calculation, and so on [1]. However, study on the shale gas reservoir material balance equation is still restricted [2]. The bulk of shale gas productivity measurement strategies for a fractured horizontal well include desorption, diffusion, and slippage. So far, few researchers have used the material balance equation to predict shale gas productivity.

The fluid flow mechanism in the shale gas reservoir is a complex mechanism for deducing analytic derivation's productivity formula and carrying out numerical simulation by establishing a mathematical model [3]. However, the material balance equation simplifies the reservoir seepage mechanism's analysis process and plays a comprehensive role in analyzing the seepage law [4,5]. As a consequence, this article predicts the analyzed gas well productivity by developing a partition

material balance equation including the matrix, natural and artificial fractures, gas, and water production rate and combining the real fractured horizontal well as a research instance; by adjusting the rate of gas supply source, provided multilevel analyzing methods to predict dynamic production of the horizontal well.

1. Establishment of the material balance equation

The complex nature of pre-existing natural fractures and their network with hydraulic fractures are combined with horizontal well completion, thus generating a fracture network as shown in Fig. 1. During production, shale gas firstly desorbs from a porous medium, diffuses and flows through natural fractures towards the artificial fractures, and finally flows to the horizontal well. Therefore, the seepage region of the material balance equation is divided into three parts: the matrix, the natural fractures, and the artificial fractures.

Fig. 1 shale gas seepage region of fractured horizontal well [6,7]

Assuming that all produced water comes from residual water after fracturing fluid flows back, the reservoir's initial water does not flow due to gas derives from rock elasticity of matrix, natural and artificial fracture; hydro-elasticity, free gas elasticity, and desorbed gas elasticity. Based on material balance theory, as pressure decreases, the material balance equation of gas and water is composed of the following parts:

The rock of matrix:

$$V_m \phi_m C_m (P_i - P_m) \tag{1}$$

The water in matrix:

$$V_m \varphi_m C_m S_{mwi} (P_i - P_m) + C_w V_{ms} (P_i - P_m) \quad (2)$$

The free gas in matrix:

$$V_m \varphi_m (1 - S_{mwc}) \frac{B_{mg} - B_{gi}}{B_{gi}} \quad (3)$$

The desorbed gas in the matrix:

$$V_m \rho_s V_L \left(\frac{P_i}{P_L + P_i} - \frac{P_m}{P_L + P_m} \right) P_{mg} \quad (4)$$

The rock of natural fracture:

$$V_f \varphi_f C_f (P_i - P_f) \quad (5)$$

The water in natural fracture:

$$V_f \varphi_f C_f S_{fwi} (P_i - P_f) \quad (6)$$

The free gas in natural fracture:

$$V_f \varphi_f (1 - S_{fwi}) \frac{B_{fg} - B_{gi}}{B_{gi}} \quad (7)$$

The rock of artificial fracture:

$$V_F C_F \varphi_F (P_i - P_F) \quad (8)$$

The water in artificial fracture:

$$V_F C_w \varphi_F S_{FW} (P_i - P_F) \quad (9)$$

The free gas in artificial fracture:

$$V_F \varphi_F (1 - S_{FW}) \frac{B_{FG} - B_{gi}}{B_{gi}} \quad (10)$$

Produced gas:

$$V_m C_m \varphi_m (P_i - P_m) \quad (11)$$

Produced water:

$$W_p B_w \quad (12)$$

According to the 12 terms, the material balance equation established as the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
W_p B_w + G_p B_{gi} &= V_m \phi_m C_m (P_i - P_m) + V_m C_m \phi_m S_{mwc} (P_i - P_m) + \\
V_m \phi_m (1 - S_{mwc}) \frac{B_{mg} - B_{gi}}{B_{gi}} &+ V_m V_L \rho_s \left(\frac{P_i}{P_L + P_i} - \frac{P_m}{P_L + P_m} \right) B_{mg} + V_f C_f \phi_f (P_i - P_f) + \\
V_f C_w \phi_f S_{fwi} (P_i - P_f) &+ V_f \phi_f (1 - S_{fwi}) \frac{B_{fg} - B_{gi}}{B_{gi}} + V_F C_F \phi_F (P_i - P_F) + \\
V_F C_w \phi_F S_{FW} (P_i - P_F) &+ V_F \phi_F (1 - S_{FW}) \frac{B_{FG} - B_{gi}}{B_{gi}}
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

2. Determine seepage division

According to the seepage law of fractured horizontal wells in shale gas reservoirs, seepage regions such as matrix region, natural and artificial fracture region are closely connected with time [8,9]. Therefore, while using a material balance equation, we cannot regard the shale gas reservoir as a closed reservoir with a constant volume. Instead, we should calculate the dynamic seepage region at different times according to the seepage law after determining the calculation method of different regions' average formation pressure. The seepage region's calculation can be simplified by using the pressure transmitting coefficient. Thus, the dynamic seepage region's volume and average formation pressure formulas are as follows:

Artificial fracture:

$$V_F(t) = 2Lhr_F \tag{14}$$

Where,

$$r_F = \sqrt{\frac{\eta_F t}{\pi}}, \quad \eta_F = \frac{K_F}{\mu_{gF} \phi_F C_{tF}}, \quad C_{tF} = C_F + C_g$$

$$P_F(t) = P_i - \frac{P_i - P_w(t)}{4 \ln \frac{r_F}{r_w}} \tag{15}$$

Natural fracture:

$$V_f(t) = 2Lhr_f \tag{16}$$

Where,

$$r_f = \sqrt{\frac{\eta_f t}{\pi}}, \quad \eta_f = \frac{K_f}{\mu_{gf} \phi_f C_{tf}}, \quad C_{tf} = C_f + C_g$$

$$P_f(t) = P_m - \frac{P_m - P_F}{4 \ln \frac{r_r}{r_F}} \quad (17)$$

Matrix:

$$V_m(t) = 2Lhr_m \quad (18)$$

Where,

$$r_m = \sqrt{\frac{\eta_m t}{\pi}}, \quad \eta_m = \frac{K_m}{\mu_{gm} \phi_m C_{tm}}, \quad C_{tm} = C_m + C_g$$

$$P_m(t) = \frac{P_i + P_F}{2} \quad (19)$$

The boundary of the dynamic seepage region is related to the parameters of the volume fracture network. The largest boundary of natural and artificial fracture is the boundary of the volume fracture network. The matrix propagates from the fracture face to the inner part, and the seepage region is associated with the number of fractures. Suppose artificial fractures are evenly distributed perpendicular to the wellbore, every fracture's half-length is the whole seepage region's half-length denoted by B ; therefore, the seepage region radius of maximum matrix pressure drop denoted as r_{max} is as follows:

$$r_{max} = \frac{BL}{L_{tF}} \quad (20)$$

Where,

$$L_{tF} = \frac{BL\phi_F}{B_F}$$

Then,

$$r_{max} = \frac{w_F}{\phi_F} \quad (21)$$

When $r_{max} > r_{max}$ the pressure drop of the whole system at the boundary; thus, the reservoir pressure will decrease overall. At that time, the average artificial fracture pressure is equal to:

$$P_F = \left(P_i - \frac{P_i - P_w(t)}{4 \ln \frac{r_F}{r_w}} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\ln \frac{r_{max}}{r_w}} + \frac{1}{\ln \frac{r_m}{r_w}} \right) \quad (22)$$

Before the range of matrix pressure drop reaches the maximum, if $r_F > B$, then $r_F=B$.

3. Water saturation determination

Assuming the reservoir has original water saturation of matrix S_{mwi} and original water saturation of natural fracture S_{fwi} , owing to imbibition's during fracturing, water saturation in a small range of matrix face contacting with the artificial fracture reaches matrix connate water saturation S_{mwc} , water saturation will not decrease during well-production (generally, for shale matrix $S_{mwi} < S_{mwc}$), sometimes the artificial fracture is along the natural fracture. Some natural fractures turn to artificial fractures, so the water saturation of natural fractures is still S_{fwi} . Water saturation of artificial fracture is related to fracturing; its formula is:

$$S_{FW} = \frac{V_{in}(1-R_r) - V_{ms}}{BLh\varphi_F} \quad (23)$$

Where,

$$\varphi_F = \frac{V_m(1-R_L)}{BLh}, \quad V_m = 2L_{tF}hd(S_{mwc} - S_{mwi})$$

Substituting last three items into the first item, we can obtain:

$$S_{FW} = 1 - \frac{2d}{W_F}(S_{mwc} - S_{mwi}) \quad (24)$$

It can be seen from the formula above that water saturation of artificial fracture mainly rely on width of fracture, depth of imbibition's, original water saturation, and connate water saturation of pore.

4. History matching and production forecast

Production forecast needs to match theoretical and historical data, mainly including gas content fitting, water production fitting, and gas production fitting. If historical matching achieves great consistency, calculations of bottom hole pressure, gas production, water production, and desorption were related to time can be conducted.

4.1 Gas content matching

Generally, the unit of shale gas content is m^3/t under standard condition, so gas content should be matching the formation condition, matrix gas in shale gas reservoir consists of free gas and absorbed gas, the absorbed gas accounts for 20%-80% of total gas, the free gas volume is constrained by formation pressure and porosity, the formula is:

$$V_Y = \frac{\varphi_m}{\rho_s B_{gi}} \quad (25)$$

According to the Langmuir Isothermal adsorption principle, the absorbed gas volume is:

$$V_E = \frac{V_L P}{P_L + P} \quad (26)$$

The total gas content is $V_g = V_Y + V_E$, by fitting analysis about the actual reservoir gas content and adsorbed gas content, parameters such as φ_m , V_L , V_p , ρ_s , P_i can be adjusted.

4.2 Water production matching

According to the hypothesis, original reservoir water cannot flow; produced water only comes from residual water of fracturing fluid, all water production is from remaining fracturing fluids. Hence, the total water production is less than the volume of flowing water in artificial fracture, as defined by the following equation:

$$W_p < [V_F(1 - R_r) - V_{ms}](1 - S_{FWC}) \quad (27)$$

4.3 Gas production matching

Combining the material balance equation with bottom hole pressure, gas production, and water production during history matching, fitting theory to practice, permeability, initial formation pressure, and connate water saturation of each system can be adjusted. During the production history process, the well will be closed, after which reservoir pressure will increase. Because pressure is the main factor in artificial fracture, the artificial fracture's average pressure is calculated after a short time well shut-in. as described in the following equation ^[16]:

$$\Delta P_F = 0.366 \frac{q_{sc} \mu_F P_{sc} Z_F T}{K_F h T_{sc} Z_{sc}} \lg \frac{2.25 \eta_f \Delta t}{r_w^2} \quad (28)$$

5. Example analysis

Taking well A-137 as an example of the model's analysis application, the calculation parameters are shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1 material balance equation calculation parameters of well *A-137*

Symbol	Unit	Value	Symbol	Unit	Value
H	M	46	C _F	1/MPa	0.0003
L	M	1000	S _{mwi}	--	0.1
B	M	300	S _{mwc}	--	0.33
H	M	1600	S _{fwi}	--	0.2
P _i	MPa	21	V _L	m ³ /t	2
φ _m	%	3.5	P _L	MPa	10
φ _f	%	0.35	ρ _s	t/m ³	2.17
K _m	mD	0.003	V _g	m ³ /t	3.84
K _f	mD	0.7	V _{in}	m ³	22000
K _F	mD	15	W _F	mm	0.5
C _m	1/MPa	0.0002	R _r	--	0.4
C _f	1/MPa	0.00025	D	mm	1

Bottom-hole pressure, daily gas production, and daily water production during the production history are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Production history of well *A-137*

The relative error of matching with the material balance equation model is substantially less than 5%, and it is used for later prediction. Based on production history, the bottom-hole pressure and water production trend are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

Fig. 3 Bottom-hole pressure over time

Fig. 4 Daily water production over time

Prediction of future production of the horizontal well based on the material balance equation is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Prediction of production parameters by the material balance equation

From Fig. 5, one can observe that the sharp drop of the bottom-hole pressure of the horizontal well in the first five years of production causes a rapid decline in daily gas production, while the daily gas production stays at $10000 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$. Afterward, the bottom-hole pressure becomes stable, and daily gas production declines slowly and reaches $2000 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$ after 40 years. During the whole process, total gas production increased rapidly at the beginning, after continued with a gradual increase. Analyzing the source of gas supply's energy contribution, bottom-hole production comprises matrix-free gas, matrix desorbed gas, natural fracture free gas, and artificial fracture free gas, calculation of four parts 'contribution proportion of total production is shown in Fig. 6. From the proportion chart of total gas production and daily gas production, one can observe that the first ten days, the produced gas is primarily coming from artificial fracture and natural fracture; after, matrix-free gas becomes the major contributor. Simultaneously, the proportion of matrix desorbed gas increases quickly to 20%, making matrix desorbed gas the main gas supply, but the fracture system's gas supply ability reduces obviously.

Fig. 6 Main proportion chart of total gas production

According to the well's production law, one can observe that the production maintenance mostly relies on the matrix-free gas amount, while desorbed gas plays a limited role. That is because absorbed gas accounted for 35% of total gas in this reservoir; if the proportion is up to 50% and 70%, desorbed gas production will account for 40% and 50% of total production, respectively. This indicates that the gas composition has a strong influence on the production laws during shale gas production.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the horizontal wells' seepage characteristics in shale gas reservoirs, the time-dependent dynamic seepage region's material balance model is established. The variation of gas production and the variation order of the structure of gas supply proportion are matched and predicted by instance and calculation; the model establishment and application analysis make the following conclusions:

1. Due to the low permeability of porous medium in shale gas formation, there is a low transmission speed of pressure drop and the seepage region's obvious time-varying tendency. Thus, while using a material balance equation, we must consider the dynamic seepage region's change rules. Furthermore, owing to the difference in pressure drop transmission speed at different seepage divisions, a partition of the material balance equation is also indispensable.
2. The change in bottom-hole pressure is the most sensitive factor in the material balance equation, particularly when the seepage region is high; a small change in pressure will cause a large wave of gas production. So, after a long production period, when the bottom-hole pressure is constant, the average pressure measurement for each partial system may need a small change. Furthermore, the produced gas is predominantly composed of matrix-free gas and adsorbed gas, and pressure changes have a major effect on the equation.

3. Dynamic seepage region, bottom-hole pressure, and change of water production are related to time. Calculation of dynamic seepage region is closely related to permeability, while the change rules of bottom hole pressure and water production rely on matching and regression; for short-run production, the result of matching and regression may not be very ideal;
4. According to the analysis of gas supply proportion structure of gas production, shale gas reflects desorption-adsorption properties up to some extent. Where the proportion of adsorbed gas in the initial reservoir condition is minimal (less than 50%), it contributes little to production (up to 20%), however when the proportion is higher (more than 50%), matrix-free gas still plays the key function.
5. The establishment of a material balance equation has several constraints, such as matrix porosity, rock density, and absorbed gas content with mutual restriction with measured gas content and reserves. In comparison, the water saturation of an artificial fracture is constrained by the fracturing parameter, fracturing fluid volume, imbibition, and so on. Water production is constrained by fracking fluid volume, flow back intensity, imbibition, and other parameters; thus, when matching, these parameters should be considered carefully.
6. The model may be used to simulate later fracking horizontal well production and to evaluate seepage region change laws.

Nomenclature

$F, f, m:$	Subscripts represent artificial fracture, natural fracture and matrix, respectively.
$r_w:$	Radius of the well hole, m.
$L_{tF}:$	Total length of artificial fracture, m.
$w_F:$	Width of artificial fracture, m.
$R_f:$	Flow back rate of fracturing fluid, decimal.
$D:$	Depth of imbibition's, m.
$\rho_s:$	Density of rock, t/m ³ .
$q_{sc}:$	Daily production of natural gas, m ³ /d.
$T:$	Temperature of formation, K.
$V_L:$	Langmuir volume, m ³ /t.
$P_L:$	Langmuir pressure, MPa.
$\mu_F:$	Viscosity of natural gas in artificial fracture, cp.
$S_{Fw}:$	Artificial fracture water saturation, decimal.
$\Delta P_F:$	Increasing pressure value in artificial fracture, MPa.
$t, \Delta t:$	Production time and shut-in time, s.
$V_{in}, V_{ms}:$	Injection volume of fracturing and imbibition volume, m ³ .
$C_w, C_g:$	Compressibility of water and natural gas respectively, 1/MPa.

P_i, P_w :	Initial formation pressure and bottom-hole pressure, MPa.
B_{gi}, B_w :	Initial volume factor of natural gas and water, decimal.
G_p, W_p :	Cumulative production of natural gas and water, m ³ /d.
S_{mwi}, S_{fwi} :	Initial water saturation, decimal.
L, h, B :	Length, thickness, and half-width of formation, m.
V_F, V_f, V_m :	Dynamic seepage volume, m ³ .
Φ_F, Φ_f, Φ_m :	Porosity, decimal.
P_F, P_f, P_m :	Average pressure, MPa.
η_F, η_f, η_m :	Pressure transmitting coefficient, m ² /s.
r_F, r_f, r_m :	Radius of seepage region, m.
C_F, C_f, C_m :	Compressibility of roc, 1/MPa.
C_{tF}, C_{tf}, C_{tm} :	Total compressibility, 1/MPa.
K_F, K_f, K_m :	Permeability, mD.
B_{Fg}, B_{fg}, B_{mg} :	Volume factor of natural gas, decimal.
$S_{mwc}, S_{fwc}, S_{Fwc}$:	Irreducible water saturation decimal.
V_Y, V_E, V_g :	Free gas content, adsorbed gas content, total gas content in matrix, m ³ /t.
P_{sc}, T_{sc}, Z_{sc} :	Pressure, temperature, gas compressibility factor in standard condition, MPa, K, decimal.

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